

FRACTURE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITES IN HIGH-SPEED TENSION

Jiang Chiping, Cao Li, Zou Zhenzhu
Wang Duo and Yao Zhongkai
(Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin, PRC)

ABSTRACT

In this paper the results of a high-speed tension experiment of the SiCw/Al composite have been reported and a simplified theoretical model has been developed to study the fracture mechanism of composites in high-speed tension. This theoretical model furnishes a new explanation about why the dynamic fracture strength of composites in high-speed tension increases by a big margin.

1. SIMPLIFIED THEORETICAL MODEL

The influence of microcracks and faults, which may exist along the interfaces between the matrix and reinforcers of composites, on the strength of the composites in conventional tension has been investigated extensively.

When a composite is subjected to high-speed tension or impact loading, the same problem has aroused a great interest in scientific research and engineering circles. Unfortunately, no report on the subject has been published in literatures. In this paper a simplified theoretical model¹ on the above problem has been developed. This model is a moving Griffith crack along the bi-material interface, and a couple of anti-plane concentrated loads act at the upper and lower faces of the crack. By using the complex variable method a closed-form solution to the problem is obtained. Through the numerical analysis of the solution, we can make the conclusion: For small Mach numbers (<0.5715) the maximum circumferential shear stress over a small circle with the crack tip as its center occurs along the line $\theta=0^\circ$; and it decreases monotonically to zero from $\theta=0^\circ$ to 180° . Therefore we may reasonably anticipate that the crack extends along its own axis. When the Mach number, however, goes up to near 0.5715, a new maximum of the circumferential stress appears at about $\theta_m=39^\circ$. As the Mach number increases further, the new maximum is keeping going up and so is θ_m . Thus we may anticipate that cracks propagating at higher speed may form kink or bifurcation, and would propagate into stronger matrices rather than along the interfaces.

It is of interest to note that in this case the effect of the interface microcracks and faults will decrease.

2. THE FRACTURE EXPERIMENT OF THE SiCw/Al SPECIMEN IN HIGH-SPEED TENSION

The specimens were of the SiC whisker reinforced aluminium composite and 6061 Al thin plates, with $2 \times 4 \text{mm}^2$ effective cross-sectional areas. The experiment was made in an England Instron Model-1186 electronic machine. Its tensile rate was 500mm/min. For comparison a conventional tensile experiment was also made. Its tensile rate was 0.5mm/min. The high-speed tensile load was recorded by a magnetic tape recorder with 14 channels.

The macroscopic fracture surfaces of the specimens were observed carefully. It was concluded that the Al specimen fracture surface showed the typical plastic fracture characteristics in spite of the existence of a little undulation. The SiCw/Al specimen fracture surfaces, however, showed the macroscopic brittle fracture characteristics. The fracture surfaces of the SiCw/Al in high-speed tension became more undulatory, which de-

monstrated that the way of cracks propagation had changed.

The fracture surfaces of the specimens were also observed in a scanning electron microscope (SEM). In the case of conventional tension there is obvious whisker pull-out, and no longitudinal crack (i.e. branching crack) as shown in Fig.1(a). In the case of high-speed tension, however, almost no whisker pull-out was observed, (Fig.1(b)), whereas branching cracks appeared in a great number, as shown in Fig.2(a) and 2(b).

From the above theoretical analysis and experiment observation we can draw a very interesting conclusion: In high-speed tension the effect of microcracks and faults along the interfaces decreases, thus the fracture strength of composites increases by a big margin, which has been verified by the data from the magnetic tape recorder. These data are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Fracture Stress Comparison (MPa)

material	CT σ	HST σ	$\Delta\sigma$
6061Al	162.2	1463.3	1301.1
SiCw/Al	372.7	3062.5	2689.8

CT=conventional tension, HST=high-speed tension σ : fracture stress, $\Delta\sigma = \text{HST}\sigma - \text{CT}\sigma$

(a) in conventional tension

(b) in high-speed tension

Fig.1 Fracture Surface Photographs of the SiCw/Al Composite under SEM

(a)

(b)

Fig.2 Branching Cracks in High-speed Tension

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